

Evaluation: Measuring intervention effects in visitor management

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AIR Brief Reports

Key findings

- Evaluation in the context of applied research is the empirical assessment of intervention effects.
- The evaluation is done through appropriate experimental designs. In the process, internal validity (theoretical meaningfulness) and external validity (statements about the real world) must often be weighed up.
- Quasi-experimental field studies are well suited if sufficient temporal and/or spatial-situational differences are taken into account.

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Introduction

Many (applied) research projects depend on testing the effectiveness of measures (interventions). This test should show whether and to what extent a measure has led to the desired result. The measuring instruments used for this should be objective, valid and reliable.

AIR is an applied research project with the aim of “exploring design options for innovative solutions for future-oriented visitor management using AI technology in an application-oriented manner”. Within the project, one work package is concerned with the evaluation. This brief report serves to deepen the understanding of our evaluation approach and at the same time make it available for other projects.

This brief report is a pragmatic introduction to the measurement of intervention effects in applied research projects. For more in-depth consideration, we refer to the more comprehensive texts on empirical social research in general (Atteslander & Cromm, 2008; Bryman, 2022; Schäfer, 2016) and on the theory of experimentation (Bortz & Döring, 2006; Sarris, 1992; Shadish et al., 2002) and evaluation (Rossi et al., 2019; Shaw et al., 2006).

Evaluation

In this project, we follow the social science understanding of evaluation research:

“Evaluation research, as a subfield of empirical research, deals with the assessment of measures or interventions” (Translated according to Bortz & Döring, 2006, p. 96).

The basis of our evaluation approach is therefore

1. the implementation of measures or interventions and
2. the evaluation of these measures and interventions.

Evaluation can take many different forms and cover many different dimensions. It therefore needs to be specified: Evaluation is often about assessing the *effectiveness* of a measure.

“Program evaluation is the application of social research methods to systematically investigate the effectiveness of social intervention programs in ways that are adapted to their political and organizational environments and are designed to inform social action to improve social conditions” (Rossi et al., 2019, p. 6)

Effectiveness describes the effectiveness (the effect) of a measure. Effect sizes can be used to determine effectiveness.

Interventions

The term intervention was originally used primarily in medical and psychotherapeutic contexts. There it describes an intervention in the form of medication or treatment (Clarke et al., 2019).

We define an intervention as “a measure whose effectiveness is assessed within the framework of an experiment or an evaluation study.” This means that a measure is considered an intervention only if it is assessed within the framework of an experiment or an evaluation. For this to happen, it must fulfil certain conditions.

In the context of visitor management, various interventions are conceivable:

- Product interventions, for example the creation of additional capacity or the opening or relocation of pathways.
- Marketing interventions related to communication, price and availability. These interventions can be classified along the lines of the INPREs framework (Schmücker et al., 2023).

Experiments

The basic principle of experimentation is: Change only one factor and leave all others constant. Then a change in the result is clearly due to the change in the circumstance.

„Today, the key feature common to all experiments is still to deliberately vary something so as to discover what happens to something else later—to discover the effects of presumed causes.” (Shadish et al., 2002, p. 3)

We call the variation of “something” the “manipulation of the independent variable” (IV). We call the change in the outcome the “variation of the dependent variable” (DV). The variation of the DV *follows* the manipulation of the IV, because the changes of the IV are interpreted as the *cause* of the changes of the DV.

In the simplest case, only one IV with two stages is defined. The subjects then end up either in the “experimental group” (with intervention) or in the “control group” (without intervention). However, any IV can also contain several levels (for example, “high level of intervention”, “low level of intervention”, “no intervention”) and there can be more than one IV (then called a multi-factorial design).

Figure 1: The basic principle of the experiment

The variation (or “variance”) of the measurement results can have different causes. We divide it into primary, secondary and tertiary variance.

The *primary variance* is the part of the variation in the measurement results that can be attributed to the change in IV. The larger the proportion of primary variance in the total variance, the better our experiment was able to show the presumed effect.

The *secondary variance* is the part of the variation of the measurement results that is due to other known influencing factors. These can be the time of day or the weather or other external influencing factors. The secondary variance should be as small as possible compared to the primary variance.

Finally, the *tertiary variance* is the part of the variation of the measurement results that is due to unknown and unsystematically fluctuating influencing factors. Generally, we do not know these influences. The tertiary variance should also be as small as possible.

Kerlinger (1964) derived recommendations for dealing with the idea of variance decomposition (Figure 2). The primary variance should be *maximised*, the secondary variance *controlled* and the tertiary variance *minimised*. Kerlinger's proposal is therefore called the *maxmincon principle*.

Figure 2: The essential contents of Kerlinger's maxmincon principle

Forms of Experiment

Experiments can essentially be differentiated according to two questions:

- Where does the experiment take place? (Lab or field experiment)
- How are the subjects assigned to the conditions? (randomised or non-randomised)

Laboratory experiments allow a very precise control of the entire experiment. This makes it possible to ensure as far as possible that the effect of the IV on the DV can be shown when it is present (internal validity). However, laboratory studies are characterised by a certain remoteness from reality: The experiments do not take place in a real environment, but in an artificial one. The transferability of the results found in the laboratory to the world outside the laboratory is therefore doubtful (external validity). *Field experiments* take place in biotic environments: “Field experiments are experiments in settings with high degrees of naturalism” (Ditlmann & Paluck, 2015, p. 128). Field experiments therefore usually have a higher external validity than laboratory experiments. This means that field experiments provide better information about real life than laboratory experiments. On the other hand, the environmental conditions in field experiments are more difficult to control than in the laboratory. The higher external validity comes at the price of a lower internal validity.

In *randomised* experiments, the subjects are randomly assigned to the conditions. Since Fisher (1935), this has been regarded as the ideal of experimental design (Clark et al., 2021). Non-randomised experiments assign subjects to conditions in other ways, such as by conditions by other means, such as quota allocation, blocking or spatiotemporal alternation. These experiments are called quasi-experiments (Shadish et al., 2002) or *natural experiments* (Dunning, 2012).

For an evaluation of visitor management systems, mainly field experiments should be considered, because for applied research a high degree of reality (external validity) seems to be more important than a maximum degree of internal validity. However, random assignment of test persons is usually not possible. Instead, temporal or spatial differentiations are made (cf. the next section).

Thus, in the context of evaluating applied research projects, we usually use quasi-field experiments.

A counterexample is the study by Mitas et al. (2023): The authors found around 270 subjects and randomly assigned them to the four experimental conditions. However, it is by no means guaranteed that the sample of 270 subjects is sufficiently representative of a defined population. Moreover, reactivity can occur here (Espeland & Sauder, 2007): The fact that the subjects are aware that they are being observed (or even actively participate in the study by filling out questionnaires or installing apps on their smartphones) can lead to an influence on the measurement results (as in the study by Tussyadiah & Wang, 2016). So here too, good internal validity (through randomisation) comes at the expense of external validity (meaningfulness for the real world).

Practical application of quasi-field experiments

The options for practical applications of quasi-field experiments are shown in figure 3. In the figure, measurements involving an intervention are shown in orange, those without an intervention in blue. Time is shown on the horizontal axis and different situations or locations are shown on the vertical axis.

The single measurement (a) is unsuitable for evaluation because the reference variable is missing. It is possible to measure how people perceive the intervention (for example, how often a sign was seen or how a website was rated), but the reference variable is missing for behavioural evaluation.

Figure 3: Practical application of quasi-field experiments

In upstream or downstream single-sequential measurement (b), a measurement is made without intervention and upstream or downstream a measurement is made with intervention. The difficulty here is that circumstances can change over time, so that the measured differences cannot be reliably attributed to the intervention. This method is therefore only suitable to a limited extent and should only be used if it can be plausibly ensured that the conditions have not changed in a relevant way over time.

With the upstream and downstream double-sequential measurement (c), the problem just mentioned still exists in principle, but here the intervention is at least embedded in two intervention-free measurements. This reduces the probability that the conditions at the time of the intervention are completely different from those before and after. If the time points with and without intervention are measured not only once, but several times, the probability decreases that systematic random errors (tertiary variance) strongly distort the results.

In parallel measurement (d), measurements are taken at the same time but in different situations or locations. Here, too, there is the problem that it cannot be ensured that the measurement results in B are different because of the intervention of A and not because of the different situation.

This can be countered by single-sequential (e) or ideally double-sequential parallel measurement (f). These procedures assume that the changes in the time course are the same or at least similar in both situations. This allows the change caused by the intervention to be triangulated. Triangulation then compares the *change* in the situation with intervention to the change in the situation without intervention.

Measures: Behaviour and perception

These measurements, in the context of visitor guidance and visitor management, can relate to either *changes in behaviour* or to *perceptions* of interventions. The measurements can be qualitative or quantitative in nature (Table 1).

Behavioural changes in the context of visitor management refer to changes in visitor flows. Perceptual aspects, on the other hand, refer to the evaluation or use of the intervention, but do not necessarily result in a change in visitor flows.

In addition, control variables can also be measured. Thus, it can help in the interpretation of the results if the quality of the experience or the satisfaction with the stay is surveyed as a control variable.

Table 1: Examples of measuring behaviour change and perception

Examples	Qualitative	Quantitative
Intervention perception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal judgement of the intervention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of hits on a website
Behaviour change	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in visitor flows • Visitors/vehicles at the measuring point • Relation of visitor numbers at different measuring points • Change in catchment areas
Control variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of the experience • Satisfaction with the stay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term visitor numbers

Effect size and significance

In order to determine the extent to which the IV has influenced the DV, a measure of the size of the measured effect must already be defined in the experimental design.

The effect size depends on the size of the difference in the DV between the conditions (factors and levels), the dispersion of the DV within and between the conditions and the number of subjects.

Table 2 shows two examples. The top row shows that in condition 1, 40% of the test persons made a particular choice and in condition 2, 60% did. The difference between the two groups is 20 percentage points. In the bottom row, the effect is represented by the mean difference. Thus, under condition 1 there is a mean of 2.3 and under condition 2 a mean of 2.5, so the mean difference is 0.2.

Table 2: Sample data for a single-factor, two-stage study

Scale level of the DV	Condition 1 („Level 1“)	Condition 2 („Level 2“)	Total
Non-metric	p = 40 %	p = 60 %	p = 50 %
Metric	$\bar{x} = 2.3,$ SD = 0.2	$\bar{x} = 2.5,$ SD = 0.2	$\bar{x} = 2.4$

However, this information alone is not sufficient to determine whether the differences presented are statistically significant (or whether they were not caused solely by random effects) and whether they are meaningful and statistically significant.

For the question of statistical significance, there are established calculation methods that consider the dispersion of the DV and the number of test persons (Bortz & Döring, 2006). These calculations can

be made not only afterwards, but also during the experimental design, for example to estimate how many test persons are needed for an assumed statistical effect size in order to reliably show an effect of the IV on the DV, if it exists. There are established software programmes for this type of power test (Faul et al., 2009).

Besides statistical significance, there is no simple formula for determining the meaningfulness of the content. Here, for example, one could ask with what effort a certain effect was generated.

Conclusion

Evaluation in the context of applied research projects involves the empirical assessment of intervention effects. Such effects can refer to changes in behaviour or evaluations of interventions.

One can study the effects of interventions using randomised or non-randomised experiments in the laboratory or in the field. None of the available options is automatically better than the others: Generally, as internal validity increases, external validity decreases and with it the informative value about the real world.

For the evaluation of applied research projects, quasi-experimental field experiments are often the means of choice. To make these experiments as meaningful as possible, temporal and situational-spatial variations can be used. The best way to do this is with more frequently changing temporal sequences, ideally in combination with parallel situations or locations.

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Notes

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